

The Administrative Problems Confronting Faculty Members At Shaqra University, Shanghai University, And Technical Colleges: A Comparative Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 24, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Shaqra University, Shanghai University, Technical Colleges, Administrative problems, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, School Shooting, School difficulties, Faculty</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4551458</p>	<p><i>The faculty members have their professional and institutional commitments at the University. They need to meet their expectations regarding time spent on teaching, research, as well as student counseling. They are expected to handle their teaching assignments with professional skill. They need to familiarize the overall organization, as well as the operations, requirements, and regulations of the university they serve. But faculty members face many problems and obstacles that affect them in doing their duties. This research focused on the problems facing teaching authorities of the chosen universities namely, Shaqra, Shanghai, and Technical Colleges. The researcher aims to answer the question: what are the most significant administrative problems faced by faculty members of Shaqra and Shanghai Universities, and Technical Colleges from their viewpoint? A questionnaire was prepared to collect data and was established according to scientific methods and steps. Using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), all data gathered were carefully analyzed. The researcher chose a random stratified sample of faculty members representing (25%) of the study population. Of 300 questionnaires distributed, 242 had been reclaimed and found to be statistically valid. Upon checking its stability and coefficient, the study concluded that there are significant differences between the administrative difficulties encountered by faculty members in terms of management control, communication, making decisions, facilities, financial resource, human relations, social service and academic affairs.</i></p>

Introduction

The role of the universities in our society is very significant. The faculty members are responsible for implementing the functions of their universities not only through teaching, writing, doing scientific research, translating, but also by developing student's academic self-concept and enhancing students' motivation and achievements (Komarraju et al, 2010).

The universities have numerous activities to perform in order to better execute their societal role with the help of their faculty members. Educational and social environment as well as the availability of effective elements such as advanced facilities and supporting elements such as administrative support is necessary factors to consider implementing its efficacy. However, the teaching authorities sometimes face many obstacles and problems that lead to non-productivity and loss of creativity. These problems may lead some university professors to emigrate outside the country for them to improve their economic conditions and to have an environment most suitable for teaching and conducting research and experimentation, thus causing brain-drain in the country.

The faculty members of Shaqra University, Shanghai University, and Technical Colleges may face many problems both at the scientific or social levels. These issues vary and more often based on the international standard of educational competencies. Therefore, this study focuses on the administrative problems of these universities and how these affect the faculty members of the universities in fulfilling their specific roles.

Statement Of The Problem

Al-Moshen(2013) study showed that majority of faculty members indicated that teaching function takes more space than the time devoted to research, scientific production and community service, which means that a

major imbalance in the academic job for them. However, the problems facing faculty members are not only on academics but also related to administrative and social aspects, as indicated by the results of the study of Al-Youssef (2011).

Al-Rawashdeh (2012) found that some faculty members indicate that there is a problem with accurate objective criteria in promotions and incentives, and in providing opportunities for holding training courses in the field of teaching and participating in specialized scientific seminars and conferences.

The lack of motivation for faculty members who are committed to the promotion system and the delay in evaluating scientific research for scientific promotions are among the most prominent problems related to the promotion system. The reason for this problem could be the lack of a clear system stipulating the motivation of the faculty, the lack of financial resources for that, and the lack of incentive programs for faculty members. (Al-Eraini, 2010)

According to Al-Eraini (2010), the most severe problems of the faculty were related to salary and incentive systems, educational aspects, the work environment, and administrative policies and practices of the college /university administration.

In China, as its economy continue to grow at an unprecedented rate, the nation as a whole has embarked on a process of substantial cultural shift. Higher education has experienced a massive growth in enrollment. But this increased demand for an educated workforce, has also caused stresses on both public and private education system particularly on the faculty members (Xiaoqing, 2011).

And just as in Saudi Arabia, faculty members in China are also faced with several challenges. To raise the institutional profile, many universities in China under Projects 985 and 211 have begun to formulate institutional policies that expect faculty members to have overseas academic experiences before professional promotion to full professorship. Consequently, some faculty members are extrinsically under pressure to seek overseas opportunities. (Qin Liu, 2015)

Another problem experienced by faculty members in some Chinese Universities is that of gender discrimination particularly in relation to hiring and in promotions, with male faculty being more favored compared to women faculty (Rhoads & Gu, 2012).

According to a study conducted by Brint in 1998, regardless of many academic debates and preoccupations of policy makers, teacher education programs still suffer from several problems and face many challenges. He indicates that today's teaching recruits higher-quality students than before, but the preparations of teachers remain poor in many places. And in the absence of further reforms of teacher training, we cannot expect great improvements in the way that school works. He claimed that poorly prepared and qualified teachers are a far more imperative problem in the developing world than they are in the industrialized realm (Brint, 1998).

Thus, this study aims to focus on the administrative problems encountered by the faculty members of Shaqra, Shanghai and Technical Colleges.

The following are the questions of the study:

1. What are the most important administrative problems facing the faculty members of the universities of Shaqra and Shanghai, and Technical Colleges in the areas of organizational leadership, control, communication, decision-making, performance evaluation, resources, human relations, local environment and community service, and academic affairs from their viewpoints?
2. What are the recommendations to overcome the difficulties encountered and reduce the administrative problems that face faculty members in the universities of Shaqra, Shanghai, and Technical Colleges?

Importance Of The Study

Faculty members are considered one of the most important factors in the deliverance of quality education. Their contributions are in the development of skills, knowledge, and behavior of the students. Therefore, having a better environment and administration is also a necessary aspect. This study is significant for the following reasons:

1. This study draws on the importance of the faculty members in society and their significant role in the success of the educational process.
2. It recognizes the problems of faculty members in higher education including administrative difficulties that is in need of further study.

3. The study presents some recommendations that may contribute to the decision-makers in the administration of universities and technical colleges for the development of higher education system, including the faculty members based on the standards of total quality and academic accreditation.
4. The study tool and results of this research may be beneficial to other researchers in determining and responding to other recurrent problems in their own organizations.
5. The study may contribute to the literature on good practices in other school, academies, and universities.
6. The findings from this study may help Shaqra University, Shanghai University, and Technical Colleges to prevent the occurrence of these problems and how to overcome these.

Purpose Of The Study

This study aims to investigate administrative difficulties facing the faculty members of Universities of Shaqra, Shanghai, and Technical Colleges. It also addresses the question of how these problems interact with one another and how it can be resolved. The researcher used interpretive stance that focuses on the viewpoint of the key players. Every individual's perceptions of these problems will affect the way the faculty member engages with teacher education and its reform thus it has to be understood that each of the respondent's will perceive these problems in the light of their own different experiences.

Study Tools

The researcher had benefited from theoretical literature and previous studies in building the idea of the current study, and these studies had helped the researcher in choosing the study method, defining terminology and theoretical anchor of the study, and in building, designing and selecting the appropriate study tool (questionnaire) in order to achieve its goals. The researcher had conducted an exploratory study through a number of personal interviews of several faculty members at the two universities (Shaqra and Shanghai) in order to ensure that the areas included in the study tool are identified. statistical methods for data analysis were determined.

Study Procedures

A- An exploratory study was conducted to identify the problems facing faculty members (Shaqra University, Shanghai University - during the first visit to the university August 2019 - and the technical colleges).
B- The study questionnaire was designed and developed in the form of Google Forms for the Arab questionnaire, wjx.cn Forms for the Chinese questionnaire, and the following procedures were also carried out:

- 1) Lifting the questionnaire on Google Drive and on <https://www.wjx.cn>, to facilitate the participation of faculty members, and answer the study questionnaire, and care was taken to put in place the necessary controls to prevent the repetition of the one-person answer.
- 2) It was agreed with some officials of the two universities and technical colleges, explaining the objectives of the study, and asking them to kindly urge the faculty members to participate.
- 3) After the preparation of the tool, the revision to its final form, verification of its validity and stability, and determination of study sample, the researcher electronically and manually distributed the questionnaire to the study population during the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020.
- 4) Participate in a number of lists of messages (WhatsApp or WeChat) for faculty members, and send a link to the questionnaire for them and request to participate.
- 5) Resend in the communication groups to confirm the participation of those who did not participate after 10 days of the first message.

Literature Review

In a study conducted in 2007 by DhaifAlzaydi, some of administrative and academic problems currently facing the development of teacher education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) are centralization, funding, university and school partnership, content of the pre-service teacher education programs and conceptualization of the linkage of theory and practice. It shows the need of decentralization and establishment of autonomous

institutions which enable faculty members to have a complete control on their perceived necessity for their respective teaching methodologies (Alzaydi, Dhaif, 2007).

Hancock & Hellowell (2003) aimed at identifying the degree of transparency by the central academic administration in modern British universities in dealing with their superiors and followers. The study concluded with some frustrations and problems facing the administration of deans and heads of academic departments, job insecurities, fear of academic, institutional status, loss of personal freedom, and a sense of non-participation in decision-making.

The study of Orata (2015) aimed to identify the problems of faculty members in the teaching of educational courses at Ohio University in the light of the application of traditional methods. The study found that the most common problems faced by faculty members are the introduction of the vocabulary of some courses, imposition of teaching students regardless of their interests, large number of students in one division, as well as the absence of recent references in the disciplines of the students and the difficulty of evaluating students. The study showed that the lack of scientific level and also the background of the preparation of the students in a pre-university education does not help the faculty members to develop creative thinking methods among students.

The Young and Shaw study (Young & Shaw, 1999) focuses on detecting factors affecting the effectiveness of teaching in the faculties of University of Northern Colorado (North Colorado University). Turning to the problems facing faculty member, and the factors that affect the effectiveness of teaching, they found out that staff members are still teaching using the traditional methods. Furthermore, the study also found that a number of faculty members have a problem in communicating and interacting with their students, thus limiting the degree of effectiveness in the teaching process. Others have a problem in organizing the course content commensurate with the educational environment in the lecture hall as they apply traditional living in teaching, and the lack of good knowledge in dealing with the appropriate pedagogical techniques.

Glick (1992) conducted a study aimed at identifying the satisfaction of academics and administrators at some American universities about their jobs. The study found that deans and heads of academic departments were dissatisfied with their jobs compared to administrators.

A study by Petty & Hatcher (1991) aimed to identify areas of satisfaction and dissatisfaction with work at technical colleges, community colleges, and colleges in Tennessee. The study found problems that led to general dissatisfaction with salaries, work, and policy towards employees. Technical colleges were one of the most dissatisfied colleges, followed by university colleges. The areas of dissatisfaction among faculty members, in addition to salaries, were the increase in the number of lectures, long working hours, and the lack of research facilities, scientific participation in conferences, and increasing the teaching load.

Data Gathering And Interpretation

The Study Sample

The study was conducted during the academic year 2019-2020 participated by 427 respondents in the course of the research. A sample had been chosen randomly.

Table 1: The sample community, numbers, and percentages of the distributed and reclaimed questionnaires

Section name	No	No. of distributed questionnaire	No. of reclaimed questionnaire	Percentage	No of nonvalid questionnaire	No of valid questionnaire
SU	100	100	86	38.40	14	86
SHU	100	100	73	24.20	27	73
TC	100	100	83	37.40	17	83
Total	300	300	242	100	58	242

Of 300 questionnaires distributed inside Shaqra University, Shanghai University, and Technical Colleges, only 242 surveys had been reclaimed and found statistically valid, 86 of which claimed from SU, 73 from SHU and 83 from TC.

Table 2: Distribution of the study sample according to some variations in the study

	Professor	Associate Professor	Assistant Professor	Lecturer	Assistant Lecturer	Total
SU	0	2	45	22	17	86
SHU	3	6	43	18	3	73
TC	0	4	35	30	14	83
Total	3	12	118	70	43	242

Table 2 shows that the total number of respondents who participated in the survey is 242, and 86 of them came from SU, 73 from SHU, and 83 from TC. The 86 SU faculty members include 2 associate professors, 45 assistant professors, 22 lecturers and 17 assistant lecturers. While in SHU, the 73 faculty members were composed of 3 professors, 6 associate professors, 43 assistant professors, 18 lecturers and 3 assistant lecturers. Lastly, the 83 faculty members of TC were consisted of 4 associate professors, 35 assistant professors, 30 lecturers and 14 assistant lecturers.

Table 3: The Respondents' Years of Experience

Section name	Less than five years	From five years to less than ten years	Ten years and more	Total
SU	25	44	16	86
SHU	12	49	12	73
TC	9	53	21	83
Total	46	146	49	242

Based on Table 3, 25 of the 86 faculty members who participated in the survey conducted at Shaqra University have less than five years of experience, 44 have six to less than ten years of practice, and 16 have more than ten years of experience. In Shanghai University, on the other hand, 12 of the participating faculty members have less than five years of practice, 49 of them have six to less than ten years of experience, and 12 have ten years and more familiarity in teaching. While based on the survey distributed in Technical Colleges, 9 of these teaching authorities who had been a partaker in this research have less than five years, 53 have five to less than ten years of experience, and 21 have ten years and more teaching experience.

Table 4: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Organization and Management

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^o	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	STF2	M3	STF3							
A.	Administrative difficulties related to organization and management:													
1.	Fewer information and data are necessary to finish the work of the members of the teaching authority.	2.23	0.95	2.26	0.69	3.12	0.79	30.8*	0.03	0.89*	0.86*	2	2	9
2.	Unclear responsibilities and stated missions for some of the member of the teaching authority.	2.02	0.96	1.97	0.91	3.34	0.63	68.45*	0.05	1.31*	1.36*	8	9	6
3.	Unfair distribution of workload by the management	2.23	0.98	2.15	0.79	3.28	0.74	44.73*	0.08	1.04*	1.13*	3	5	7
4.	Difficulty in dealing with departments and colleges.	2.02	0.99	2.05	0.86	3.14	0.83	41.18*	0.03	1.12*	1.09*	9	7	8
5.	Centralization at the work management inside the college.	2.09	1.00	2.19	0.76	4.08	1.13	107*	0.10	1.99*	1.89*	5	3	2
6.	A lot of routine procedures in the execution of works.	2.24	0.97	2.41	0.78	3.99	1.23	73.41*	0.17	1.74*	1.58*	1	1	5
7.	Incapability of some department heads to achieve their departmental objectives and targets.	2.14	1.00	2.04	0.87	4.08	0.98	118.8*	0.10	1.94*	2.04*	4	8	3
8.	The absence of moral support and financial incentives.	2.08	0.95	2.18	0.77	4.05	1.07	113.3*	0.10	1.97*	1.87*	6	4	4
9.	The Absence of clear objective and its measurements in hiring	2.07	0.98	2.05	0.86	4.14	1.11	119.9*	0.01	2.07*	2.09*	7	6	1

management and supervising positions.														
TOTAL	2.13	0.36	2.15	0.45	3.69	0.47	363.8*	0.02	1.57*	1.55*				

According to Table 4, the total score between SU and SHU had no statistically significant difference, but SU vs. TC and SHU vs. TC both have an indicative difference with 1.57 and 1.55 total averages score. It is also evident that this difference is represented in the phrases 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 as shown in the table above.

Table 5: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Censorship

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^o	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3								
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3		SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
B.	Administrative difficulties related to censorship													
10.	Unclear censorship targets that affect faculty members' performance.	1.63	0.49	1.68	0.55	3.66	0.61	363.3*	0.06	2.03*	1.98*	1	3	9
11.	Inequality in the faculty members' accountability and the management's censorship on the performance of the member of the teaching authority.	1.62	0.72	1.85	0.46	3.49	0.50	257.2*	0.23	1.88*	1.64*	2	1	6
12.	The limitations and the	1.56	0.50	1.81	0.49	3.70	0.62		0.25			4	2	

	pressures which are imposed by the external management.							386.3*		2.14*	1.89*			7
13.	Different personal perceptions about the censorship principle.	1.48	0.50	1.60	0.57	3.66	0.61	391.9*	0.13	2.19*	2.06*	5	5	8
14.	Ineffective management censorship that affects the performance of the teaching authorities.	1.58	0.50	1.66	0.56	3.80	0.71	364.8*	0.08	2.21*	2.14*	3	4	2
TOTAL		1.57	0.27	1.72	0.34	3.66	0.29	1258*	0.15	2.09*	1.94*			

Table 5 demonstrates that there is no statistical difference between SU and SHU based on the administrative difficulties related to censorship with the average mean of 0.15. But in SU vs. SHU and SHU vs. TC, it can be observed that there are statistical differences with the total averages of 2.09 and 1.94 in favor of SU vs. SHU.

Table 6: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Communication

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" [∂]	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3							
C.	Administrative difficulties related to communication													
15.	Lack of initiative in developing communication skills of the members of the teaching authority.	2.09	1.21	2.25	1.45	2.92	0.93	10.94*	0.15	0.82*	0.67*	1	1	5
16.	A high percentage of vernacular usage in the	2.09	1.20	1.73	0.96	2.99	0.93	30.7*	0.37	0.90*	1.26*	2	5	4

	management communication operation.													
17.	Unavailable modern systems to communicate (for example the interaction sites).	2.02	0.99	1.90	0.99	2.87	0.97	23*	0.12	0.84*	0.96*	3	4	6
18.	The inflexibility in the communication operation between the management and teaching authorities.	1.97	1.19	2.05	1.00	3.53	1.29	46.06*	0.09	1.57*	1.48*	4	3	2
19.	The absence of secretary for the departments to easily deal with the teaching authority and management.	1.79	1.10	2.21	1.18	3.64	1.31	54.51*	0.41	1.85*	1.43*	5	2	1
20.	Lack of open communication channels between the college and the local organizations.	1.52	0.50	1.51	0.53	3.23	1.28	108.5*	0.02	1.71*	1.72*	6	6	3
TOTAL		1.91	0.42	1.94	0.54	3.19	0.72	133.2*	0.03	1.28*	1.25*			

Table 6 shows that there is no statistical difference between SU and SHU based on the administrative difficulties related to communication with an average mean of 0.03. However, it can be seen in SU vs. SHU and SHU vs. TC that there are statistical difference with the both axes with the total averages of 1.28 and 1.25 in favor of SU vs. TC.

Table 7: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Decision Making

	SU	SHU	TC	"F" ^δ	SCHEFFE TESTS	ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS

		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3	
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3								
D.	Administrative difficulties related to decision making														
21.	The management of the college is characterized by the ability to take risk in the decisions and responsibilities	1.29	0.46	3.04	1.28	3.12	0.79	113.8*	1.75	1.83*	0.08	17	17	13	
22.	The college depends on the newest and accurate information in taking the decisions.	1.44	0.50	1.51	0.50	3.51	0.77	306*	0.06	2.06*	2.00*	9	11	5	
23.	The less knowledge of the decision maker by taking cyclic way.	1.44	0.50	1.48	0.50	3.53	0.75	324.7*	0.04	2.09*	2.05*	10	8	4	
24.	Decisions are not effectively communicated in suitable time.	1.50	0.50	1.41	0.50	3.16	0.85	191.7*	0.09	1.66*	1.75*	5	4	12	
25.	Lack of commitment to implement the decisions made.	1.45	0.50	1.48	0.50	3.20	0.82	207.5*	0.03	1.75*	1.73*	8	7	10	
26.	The weakness in taking the management decision depending on the information and the data in operation.	1.35	0.48	1.45	0.50	3.07	0.88	181.4*	0.10	1.72*	1.62*	16	5	14	
27.	When taking the decisions which are related to the college, the regulations and the systems were applied.	1.40	0.49	1.38	0.49	3.05	1.40	90.68*	0.01	1.65*	1.66*	13	1	15	
TOTAL		1.41	0.49	1.68	0.61	3.23	0.89	60.53	-0.27	-1.82	-1.55	1.41			

Based on Table 7, there is a statistically significant difference between responses where the value of "F" is greater than the tabular value. At a level of significance which is 0.05, the resulted differences were between Shaqra University and Shanghai University non-statistically significant values and between Shaqra University and Technical Colleges a statistically significant in favor of Technical Colleges - Shanghai University and the Technical Colleges statistically significant in favor of technical colleges

Table 8: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to the Central Work of Management

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^δ	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3							
E.	Central works of management inside the colleges													
28.	The management difficulties which are related in the organizational environment and evaluating the performance.	1.41	0.18	1.68	0.26	3.23	0.45	788.4*	0.27	1.82*	1.56*	12	15	7
29.	The member of the teaching authority increases the pressure in instruction.	1.37	0.49	1.38	0.49	1.47	0.50	0.97	0.01	0.10	0.09	15	3	17
30.	An absence of the program of the teaching authority in receiving the new members.	1.43	0.50	1.68	0.47	3.59	0.56	437*	0.25	2.16*	1.91*	11	16	3
31.	The member of the teaching authority was not considered by the systems and regulations	1.52	0.50	1.47	0.50	3.22	0.64	261.8*	0.06	1.69*	1.75*	3	6	8

32.	Less experience for most of the managers impedes the work with the members of the teaching authority.	1.40	0.49	1.38	0.49	3.20	0.62	309.6*	0.01	1.81*	1.82*	14	2	9
33.	The absence of the facilities which are related to the timing of the work (courses – library timing).	1.51	0.50	1.51	0.50	3.34	0.63	301.2*	0.00	1.83*	1.83*	4	10	6
34.	More conferences and courses are necessary for the member of the teaching authority.	1.50	0.50	1.53	0.50	4.49	0.65	776.9*	0.03	2.99*	2.96*	6	12	1
35.	The temporary contract which is leading to absence in security and job stability.	1.59	0.49	1.51	0.50	4.48	0.65	758.5*	0.09	2.89*	2.98*	1	9	2
36.	Unknown basis of performance evaluation of members of the teaching authority.	1.56	0.50	1.59	0.50	1.93	1.01	6.758*	0.03	0.37	0.34	2	13	16
37.	Subjective in evaluating the college for the performance of the member of the teaching authority.	1.48	0.50	1.59	0.50	3.19	0.74	215.5*	0.11	1.72*	1.60*	7	14	11
TOTAL		1.58	0.50	1.56	0.50	3.16	0.99	136.5*	0.02	1.58*	1.60*			

Table 8 shows the administrative difficulties related to the central work of collegiate management. It also demonstrates that there is statistically significant difference between the responses of the sample population. The differences were between Shaqra University and Shanghai University non-statistically significant values and between Shaqra University and Technical Colleges a statistically significant in favor of Technical Colleges. Shanghai University and the

Technical Colleges are statistically significant for technical colleges, except for the phrase 36 although there was a difference between the three samples in this phrase. However, the transparency test did not show a sign of these differences.

Table 9: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Human, Material and Financial Resources

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^δ	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3							
F.	Administrative difficulties related to human, material, and the financial resources													
38.	The late approval of the financial rights.	1.41	0.18	1.68	0.26	3.23	0.45	788.4*	0.27	1.82*	1.56*	12	15	7
39.	Fewer rooms, laps, and workshops which can contribute to the teaching operation.	1.37	0.49	1.38	0.49	1.47	0.50	0.97	0.01	0.10	0.09	15	3	17
40.	Fewer services in the college environment which contribute to the decrease of the faculty members' capability.	1.43	0.50	1.68	0.47	3.59	0.56	437*	0.25	2.16*	1.91*	11	16	3
41.	Lack of facilities needed by teaching authorities	1.52	0.50	1.47	0.50	3.22	0.64	261.8*	0.06	1.69*	1.75*	3	6	8
42.	An absence of the scientific and educational description for the building.	1.40	0.49	1.38	0.49	3.20	0.62	309.6*	0.01	1.81*	1.82*	14	2	9

43.	Unavailability of a restaurant or private places for the cars suitable for the member of the teaching authority.	1.51	0.50	1.51	0.50	3.34	0.63	301.2*	0.00	1.83*	1.83*	4	10	6
44.	The college is not helping the member of the teaching authority to grow up professionally.	1.50	0.50	1.53	0.50	4.49	0.65	776.9*	0.03	2.99*	2.96*	6	12	1
45.	The procedures in upgrading the members of the teaching authority.	1.59	0.49	1.51	0.50	4.48	0.65	758.5*	0.09	2.89*	2.98*	1	9	2
46.	The standards for hiring management positions in the college do not exist.	1.56	0.50	1.59	0.50	1.93	1.01	6.758*	0.03	0.37	0.34	2	13	16
47.	The inefficient leaders in the management level	1.48	0.50	1.59	0.50	3.19	0.74	215.5*	0.11	1.72*	1.60*	7	14	11
TOTAL		1.58	0.50	1.56	0.50	3.16	0.99	136.5*	0.02	1.58*	1.60*			

Table 9 illustrates that there is a statistically significant difference between responses where the value of "F" is greater than the tabular value at a level of significance (0.05). The differences were between Shaqra University and Shanghai University non-statistically significant data, the Shaqra University and the Technical Colleges are statistically significant for Technical Colleges and Shanghai University and Technical Colleges for Technical Colleges.

Table 10: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Human, Material and Financial Resources

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^o	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3							
G.	Administrative difficulties related to human relations													
48.	It seems to have no empathy or concern to the members of teaching authority when facing the problems.	1.45	0.15	1.49	0.18	3.26	0.35	1476*	0.04	1.81*	1.77*	2	2	3
49.	The humanity relations are weakening which is needed to be available in the academic work.	1.33	0.47	1.37	0.49	4.16	0.59	793.9*	0.04	2.83*	2.79*	5	4	1
50.	The censorship on the member of the teaching authority which is searching for his/her mistakes.	1.42	0.50	1.45	0.50	4.05	0.88	433.2*	0.03	2.63*	2.60*	4	3	2
51.	The incentives for the member of the teaching authority do not exist.	1.43	0.50	1.36	0.48	3.24	0.88	219.8*	0.07	1.81*	1.88*	3	5	5
52.	The threat and the punishment methods make the morale of the member of the teaching authority become weak.	1.67	0.47	1.52	0.50	3.24	0.84	186.4*	0.15	1.57*	1.72*	1	1	4

TOTAL	1.41	0.49	1.52	0.50	3.29	0.74	260.4*	0.11	1.88*	1.77*			
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Based on Table 10, it can be realized that there is a statistically significant difference between the responses of all faculty members participated in the research. The differences were evident between Shaqra University-Shanghai University non-statistically significant values and Shaqra University-Technical Colleges statistical significance.

Table 11: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Local Environment and Social Service

		SU		SHU		TC		"F" ^o	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
		*1		*2		*3			SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC	M1	M2	M3
		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3							
H.	Administrative difficulties related to the local environment and social service													
53	The organization between the college and the local society does not exist.	1.45	0.25	1.44	0.25	3.60	0.40	1316*	0.01	2.14*	2.15*	8	5	1.45
54	Lack of supervision on the educational curriculum for the morality of the society.	4.26	0.84	1.40	0.49	2.07	0.96	283.5*	2.86*	2.18*	0.68*	1	8	4.26
55	The college is not participating in social problems.	1.57	0.50	1.42	0.50	1.99	0.99	13.6*	0.15	0.42	0.56*	4	6	1.57
56	The prestige of the university teacher becomes less.	1.55	0.50	1.42	0.50	1.80	0.98	5.686*	0.12	0.25	0.37	6	7	1.55
57	The positivity of the society to serve the university.	1.60	0.49	1.70	0.46	2.02	1.00	8.182*	0.09	0.42*	0.33	2	1	1.60

58	Understanding the role of the University	1.55	0.50	1.68	0.47	2.04	1.01	10.62*	0.14	0.49*	0.35	7	2	1.55
59	The strategic plan for the university education which is compatible with the societal needs does not exist.	1.56	0.50	1.51	0.50	2.07	0.96	16.49*	0.05	0.51*	0.57*	5	4	1.56
60	Not existing programs which are serving the society and the continuous learning like training during the service workshops.	1.59	0.49	1.55	0.50	2.08	0.98	14.65*	0.05	0.49*	0.54*	3	3	1.59
TOTAL		1.65	0.48	1.70	0.46	1.88	0.97	2.58	0.05	0.23	0.18			

According to Table 11, the administrative difficulties related to the local environment and community service has a statistically significant difference between the responses of the partakers. Except for the phrase number 54, the differences were statistically significant in favor of Shaqra University, Shaqra University, and Technical Colleges. It is evident on numbers 53, 54, 57, 58, 59 and 60.

Table 12: The Administrative Problems Based on Difficulties Related to Academic Affairs

	SU	SHU	TC	"F" ^δ	SCHEFFE TESTS			ORDER WITHIN DIMENSIONS		
	*1	*2	*3					M1	M2	M3

		M1	STD 1	M2	ST F2	M3	STF3		SU vs. SHU	SU vs. TC	SHU vs. TC			
I.	Administrative difficulties related to the academic affair													
61	Unavailability of the references and periodicals in the library.	1.92	0.22	1.55	0.21	1.99	0.42	47.05*	0.37	0.08	0.44*	7	9	8
62	Discouragement in participating the conferences.	2.15	1.30	1.85	1.00	1.73	0.96	3.209*	0.30	0.42	0.11	4	7	9
63	Unavailability of relaxing academic weather for the member of the teaching authority.	2.07	0.96	1.88	1.00	2.11	1.18	1.06	0.19	0.04	0.23	5	6	7
64	Lack of resources	2.50	0.50	2.48	0.50	2.51	0.50	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.03	2	2	5
65	Abundant number of students	2.48	0.50	2.42	0.50	2.42	0.50	0.32	0.05	0.06	0.00	3	3	6
66	Not taking the opinions and the suggestions of the member of the teaching authority in making modifications to the educational curriculum and the learning plans.	2.51	0.50	2.59	0.50	2.55	0.50	0.48	0.08	0.04	0.03	1	1	4
67	Lack of expertise on the particular subject being taught.	1.36	0.48	1.95	1.43	3.05	1.00	25.27*	0.58	1.69*	1.10*	9	5	1
68	The unavailability of the university's assistance for the beginner teaching authority member.	1.81	0.96	1.70	0.94	3.01	0.99	45.94*	0.12	1.20*	1.31*	8	8	3

69	The teaching authority member starts to transfer from researcher to teacher only.	1.99	0.99	2.01	1.06	3.01	0.99	27.26*	0.03	1.02*	1.00*	6	4	2
TOTAL		2.09	0.56	2.05	1.42	2.49	0.49	36.34*	0.04	0.40	0.44*			

According to Table 12, there was a statistically significant difference between the responses of faculty members regarding the administrative difficulties related to academic affairs. It is evident in numbers 61, 62, 67, 68 and 69 while there are no significant differences in expressions 63, 64, 65 and 66. The indicative difference is in favor to Shanghai University vs. Technical Colleges.

The Psychometric Properties of the Questionnaire

Table 13: Description of study tool (parts, axes, sequence of phrases and number of phrases)

		Serial phrases	Number of Phrases
1	Less information and the data which is necessary to finish the work of the members of the teaching authority.	1-9	9
2	The unclear responsibilities and missions for some member of the faculty members.	10-14	5
3	The uneven distribution of management information.	15-20	6
4	The difficulty in dealing between the departments and the colleges.	21-27	7
5	The centralization of work management inside the colleges.	28-37	10
6	A lot of routine procedures at executing the management work.	38-47	10
7	The weakness situation of some department leaders in the ideal way to do the purposes comes true.	48-52	5
8	The absence of the spirits and the financial incentives which decrease the production of the members of the teaching authority.	53-60	8
9	The absence of the clearance and the objective measurements in hiring the management and the supervising positions.	61-69	9

Table 14: Correlation coefficients between the score of each statement and the degree to which the term belongs

Organization and leadership		Control		Connection		Make decision		Performance evaluation		Human and material resources		Human relations		Local environment		Academic Affairs	
No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr	No.	Corr
1	0.704	10	0.564	15	0.687	21	0.664	28	0.608	38	0.794	48	0.702	53	0.683	61	0.725
2	0.482	11	0.741	16	0.737	22	0.708	29	0.668	39	0.628	49	0.788	54	0.816	62	0.746
3	0.668	12	0.672	17	0.646	23	0.788	30	0.696	40	0.575	50	0.652	55	0.641	63	0.670
4	0.590	13	0.698	18	0.713	24	0.718	31	0.691	41	0.457	51	0.719	56	0.749	64	0.720
5	0.691	14	0.727	19	0.633	25	0.761	32	0.754	42	0.677	52	0.805	57	0.672	65	0.796
6	0.741			20	0.797	26	0.655	33	0.638	43	0.685			58	0.694	66	0.742
7	0.730					27	0.613	34	0.769	44	0.663			59	0.660	67	0.640
8	0.741							35	0.713	45	0.649			60	0.786	68	0.796
9	0.763							36	0.627	46	0.610					69	0.853
								37	0.721	47	0.807						

Table 14 shows that the values of correlation coefficients calculated for each axis are calculated separately with the degree of the axis to which those terms belong higher than the tabular value at an indication level (0.01) indicating the internal consistency of the questionnaire.

Table 15: Stability coefficients of the axes

Administrative issues related to																	
Organization and leadership		Control		Connection		Make decision		Performance evaluation		Human and material resources		Human relationships		Local environment		Academic Affairs	
No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R
1	0.817	10	0.756	15	0.803	21	0.809	28	0.816	38	0.805	48	0.839	53	0.838	61	0.815
2	0.825	11	0.811	16	0.795	22	0.752	29	0.805	39	0.816	49	0.744	54	0.854	62	0.813
3	0.821	12	0.836	17	0.816	23	0.816	30	0.805	40	0.831	50	0.803	55	0.844	63	0.810
4	0.824	13	0.794	18	0.838	24	0.816	31	0.816	41	0.847	51	0.844	56	0.821	64	0.809
5	0.809	14	0.845	19	0.812	25	0.795	32	0.817	42	0.839	52	0.679	57	0.843	65	0.804
6	0.826			20	0.776	26	0.812	33	0.769	43	0.794			58	0.767	66	0.827
7	0.794					27	0.816	34	0.809	44	0.813			59	0.805	67	0.848
8	0.824							35	0.794	45	0.846			60	0.817	68	0.831
9	0.769							36	0.825	46	0.825					69	0.739
								37	0.763	47	0.798						

It is evident from Table 15 that the values of the coefficients of the stability of the terms are less than the coefficient of axis firmness to which the individual belongs which means all statements are consistent; this indicates that the study tool enjoys a high degree of constancy. Thus, results can be depended upon and trusted. The overall stability coefficient of the study tool is 0.884.

Main Findings And Recommendations

Based on the results gathered and interpreted, there are significant differences between the various administrative problems encountered by the faculty members of the three study groups, Shaqra University, Shanghai University and Technical Colleges. Thus it demonstrates the importance of understanding and interpreting the real administrative difficulties that hinder the full capability of the teaching authorities. Without their maximum efficiency, it will be difficult to deliver quality education not just to the respective participating universities but also to all universities worldwide.

In line with this, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The attention to the human resource development more than the administrative work in educational institutions, especially in the universities because of their importance in the high level of morale among faculty members.
2. To use modern electronic techniques for better teaching efficiency, convenience, a speed of delivery and cost reduction.
3. The need to reconsider the salary scale, taking into account the scientific production of the faculty member to grant additional annual increases commensurate with the scientific production in both quantity and quality regarding scientific research published or accepted for publication or the level of scientific authorship.
4. Encourage to hold or conduct effective courses and the 100% participation of faculty members in universities and technical colleges to these conferences.
5. To provide opportunities for faculty members to participate effectively in the decision-making process of the educational process.
6. To ensure the availability of the necessary facilities and equipment for University Education and the provision of comfortable offices, modern educational techniques, and laboratories that are well equipped.
7. Adopting a clear strategy for the development of programs and curricula so as to achieve the desired social objectives, keep abreast of current technological trends and information developments.
8. The administration of the University should control the number of students in each division, but not exceed the reasonable limit so that faculty members can address the possible occurrence of problems and issues.
9. Taking care of the selection of students applying for admission, by checking the availability of interview conditions, rather than being a formality in many cases.
10. Make excellence in teaching and community service a criterion for promotion, in addition to scientific research.
11. Executing universities for the comprehensive health insurance program for faculty members internally and externally, providing a decent education for their children, and establishing social and recreational clubs for the educational staff.

12. Conduct more follow-up studies; learn more about the problems of faculty members in other colleges and universities, and find out the similarities and differences, to identify the problems faced by all teaching authorities in Saudi Universities, which helps to find comprehensive solutions for all universities.
13. The administration should invest on the internationalization of the faculty.
14. Provide an atmosphere or policy of gender equality or no discrimination in relation to faculty promotions and in holding key positions in the university.

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